

LITERARY REVIEW OF THE MAIN DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS OF PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF SALIVARY GLANDS OF DIFFERENT GENESIS

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Relevance. Differential diagnosis of diseases united by the common symptom of hyposalivation is quite complex, primarily due to the many reasons affecting the regulatory processes of salivation. As a rule, the salivary glands are affected secondary to diseases of the internal organs, and early signs of pathology of the salivary glands remain unnoticed for a long time [7]. Dysfunction of the salivary glands quite often develops against the background of endocrine pathology [11, 12, 3]. The use of general clinical research methods related to general methods, such as questioning, examination, palpation, and laboratory research methods are a simple and fairly informative method of diagnosis, helping to determine not only the presence of a pathological process, but also a number of concomitant diseases.

Target- based on a thorough analysis of specialized literature, determine the most informative and accessible methods for examining patients with various diseases of the salivary glands.

Materials and methods of research. A literature review of scientific studies over the past 5 years was conducted.

Thus, the lysozyme flow rate, determined from a single sample of saliva by the calculation method, is not an objective criterion for the value of the true flow rate.

To level out the results of measuring the concentration of salivary lysozyme due to the rapid variability of the secretion of this enzyme, it is recommended to take 3 saliva samples every 10 minutes with a 30-minute interval between the start of collection.

According to some researchers, it has been revealed that when studying oral resistance factors, most researchers limit themselves to determining the level of lysozyme in saliva. At the same time, for these purposes, the level of B lysine and sIgA should be studied.

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